

Closed Forms of Two Types of Fractional Integrals

Chii-Huei Yu

School of Mathematics and Statistics, Zhaoqing University, Guangdong, China

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14243360>

Published Date: 29-November-2024

Abstract: In this paper, based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we find the closed forms of two types of fractional integrals by using some methods. Moreover, our results are generalizations of classical calculus results.

Keywords: Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus, new multiplication, fractional analytic functions, closed forms, fractional integrals.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fractional calculus is the theory of non-integer derivative and integral. However, the definition of fractional derivative is not unique. Common definitions include Riemann Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative, Caputo fractional derivative, Grunwald Letnikov (G-L) fractional derivative and Jumarie's modification of R-L fractional derivative [1-5]. In the past decades, fractional calculus has been widely used in continuum mechanics, quantum mechanics, electronic engineering, fluid science, viscoelasticity, control theory, dynamics, financial economics and other fields [6-17].

In this paper, based on Jumarie type of R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we use some techniques to find the closed forms of the following two types of fractional integrals:

$$\left({}_0 I_x^\alpha \right) \left[-\frac{1}{2} \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \operatorname{Ln}_\alpha(1 + 2r \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha (-1)} \right) \right],$$

and

$$\left({}_0 I_x^\alpha \right) \left[\frac{1}{2} \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \operatorname{Ln}_\alpha(1 + 2r \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha (-1)} \right) \right],$$

where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and r is a real number. In fact, our results are generalizations of ordinary calculus results.

II. PRELIMINARIES

At first, we introduce the fractional calculus used in this paper and its properties.

Definition 2.1 ([18]): Let $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x_0 be a real number. The Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville (R-L) α -fractional derivative is defined by

$$\left({}_{x_0} D_x^\alpha \right) [f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dx} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)-f(x_0)}{(x-t)^\alpha} dt, \quad (1)$$

And the Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville α -fractional integral is defined by

$$\left({}_{x_0} I_x^\alpha \right) [f(x)] = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{x_0}^x \frac{f(t)}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad (2)$$

where $\Gamma(\)$ is the gamma function.

Proposition 2.2 ([19]): If α, β, x_0, C are real numbers and $\beta \geq \alpha > 0$, then

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[(x - x_0)^\beta] = \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{\beta-\alpha}, \tag{3}$$

and

$$({}_{x_0}D_x^\alpha)[C] = 0. \tag{4}$$

Definition 2.3 ([20]): Let x, x_0 and a_k be real numbers for all k , and $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. If the function $f_\alpha: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be expressed as $f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{k\alpha}$, then we say that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ is α -fractional analytic at $x = x_0$.

Next, we introduce a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions.

Definition 2.4 ([21]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. Assume that $f_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ and $g_\alpha(x^\alpha)$ are two α -fractional power series at $x = x_0$,

$$f_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{k\alpha}, \tag{5}$$

$$g_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{b_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{k\alpha}. \tag{6}$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) &= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{a_k}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{k\alpha} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{m=0}^\infty \frac{b_m}{\Gamma(m\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^{m\alpha} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{1}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m \right) (x - x_0)^{k\alpha}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} f_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha g_\alpha(x^\alpha) &= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{a_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha k} \otimes_\alpha \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{b_k}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha k} \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{1}{k!} \left(\sum_{m=0}^k \binom{k}{m} a_{k-m} b_m \right) \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}(x - x_0)^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha k}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Definition 2.5 ([22]): Assume that $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and x is a real number. The α -fractional exponential function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{x^{k\alpha}}{\Gamma(k\alpha+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{1}{k!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha k}. \tag{9}$$

And the α -fractional cosine and sine function are defined as follows:

$$\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^k x^{2k\alpha}}{\Gamma(2k\alpha+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^k}{(2k)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha 2k}, \tag{10}$$

and

$$\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^k x^{(2k+1)\alpha}}{\Gamma((2k+1)\alpha+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{(-1)^k}{(2k+1)!} \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} x^\alpha \right)^{\otimes_\alpha (2k+1)}. \tag{11}$$

Theorem 2.6 (fractional Euler's formula)([23]): If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and $i = \sqrt{-1}$, then

$$E_\alpha(ix^\alpha) = \cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + i \sin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \tag{12}$$

Notation 2.7: If the complex number $z = p + iq$, where p, q are real numbers. p is the real part of z , and denoted by $\text{Re}(z)$; q is the imaginary part of z , and denoted by $\text{Im}(z)$.

III. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we use some methods to find the closed forms of two types of fractional integrals. At first, a lemma is needed.

Lemma 3.1: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and r is a real number, then

$$\text{Re}[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \text{Ln}_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)]$$

$$= [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha). \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Im}[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \\ &= r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ & \quad + [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Proof Since

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha) \\ &= (1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + ir\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + ir\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)) - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) - ir\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \\ &= (1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + ir\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha \left[\frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) + i \cdot \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) \right] - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) - ir\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Re}[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \\ &= [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ & \quad - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} & \operatorname{Im}[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \\ &= r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ & \quad + [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad \text{q.e.d.}$$

Theorem 3.2: If $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, and r is a real number, then

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[-r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) \right] \\ &= [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & ({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) \right] \\ &= r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} L n_\alpha(1 + 2r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ & \quad + [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \arctan_\alpha \left(r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + r\cos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)} \right) - r\sin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Proof Since

$$({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha ({}_0D_x^\alpha)[rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \right] = (1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha L n_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha). \quad (18)$$

It follows that

$$({}_0I_x^\alpha)[Ln_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha riE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] = (1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha Ln_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha). \quad (19)$$

And hence,

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[\frac{1}{2} Ln_\alpha(1 + 2rcos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) + r^2) + i \cdot arctan_\alpha(rsin_\alpha(Ax^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + rcos_\alpha(Ax^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)}) \right] \\ &\quad \otimes_\alpha [-rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) + ircos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \\ &= (1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha Ln_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha). \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[-r sin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} Ln_\alpha(1 + 2rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha arctan_\alpha(rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)}) \right] \\ &= Re[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha Ln_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \\ &= [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} Ln_\alpha(1 + 2rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ &\quad - rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha arctan_\alpha(rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)}) - rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha). \quad (\text{by Lemma 3.1}) \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} &({}_0I_x^\alpha) \left[rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} Ln_\alpha(1 + 2rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) - rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha arctan_\alpha(rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)}) \right] \\ &= Im[(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) \otimes_\alpha Ln_\alpha(1 + rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)) - rE_\alpha(ix^\alpha)] \\ &= rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha \frac{1}{2} Ln_\alpha(1 + 2rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha) + r^2) \\ &\quad + [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)] \otimes_\alpha arctan_\alpha(rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha) \otimes_\alpha [1 + rcos_\alpha(x^\alpha)]^{\otimes_\alpha(-1)}) - rsin_\alpha(x^\alpha). \quad (\text{by Lemma 3.1}) \end{aligned}$$

q.e.d.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, based on Jumarie’s modified R-L fractional calculus and a new multiplication of fractional analytic functions, we use some methods to obtain the closed forms of two types of fractional integrals. Moreover, our results are generalizations of the results in traditional calculus. In the future, we will continue to use our methods to solve the problems in applied mathematics and fractional differential equations.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Das, Functional Fractional Calculus, 2nd ed., Springer-Verlag, 2011.
- [2] S. G. Samko, A. A. Kilbas, O. I. Marichev, Fractional Integrals and Derivatives Theory and Applications, Gordon and Breach, New York, 1993.
- [3] K. B. Oldham and J. Spanier, The Fractional Calculus, Academic Press, Inc., 1974.
- [4] K. S. Miller and B. Ross, An introduction to the Fractional Calculus and Fractional Differential Equations, A Wiley-Interscience Publication, John Wiley & Sons, New York, USA, 1993.
- [5] I. Podlubny, Fractional Differential Equations, Academic Press, San Diego, Calif, USA, 1999.

- [6] E. Soczkiewicz, Application of fractional calculus in the theory of viscoelasticity, *Molecular and Quantum Acoustics*, Vol.23, pp.397-404, 2002.
- [7] V. E. Tarasov, *Mathematical economics: application of fractional calculus*, *Mathematics*, 2020, 8(5), 660.
- [8] R. S. Barbosa, J. A. T. Machado, and I. M. Ferreira, PID controller tuning using fractional calculus concepts, *Fractional Calculus & Applied Analysis*, Vol. 7, No. 2, pp. 119-134, 2004.
- [9] Hasan A. Fallahgoul, Sergio M. Focardi and Frank J. Fabozzi, *Fractional Calculus and Fractional Processes with Applications to Financial Economics*, Academic Press, 2017.
- [10] B. Carmichael, H. Babahosseini, SN Mahmoodi, M. Agah, The fractional viscoelastic response of human breast tissue cells, *Physical Biology*, 2015,12(4), 046001.
- [11] Mohd. Farman Ali, Manoj Sharma, Renu Jain, An application of fractional calculus in electrical engineering, *Advanced Engineering Technology and Application*, Vol. 5, No. 2, pp, 41-45, 2016.
- [12] Teodor M. Atanacković, Stevan Pilipović, Bogoljub Stanković, Dušan Zorica, *Fractional Calculus with Applications in Mechanics: Vibrations and Diffusion Processes*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 2014.
- [13] J. T. Machado, *Fractional Calculus: Application in Modeling and Control*, Springer New York, 2013.
- [14] L. Debnath, Recent applications of fractional calculus to science and engineering, *International Journal of Mathematics and Mathematical Sciences*, 2003, 54, pp. 3413-3442.
- [15] M. F. Silva, J. A. T. Machado, and I. S. Jesus, Modelling and simulation of walking robots with 3 dof legs, in *Proceedings of the 25th IASTED International Conference on Modelling, Identification and Control (MIC '06)*, pp. 271-276, Lanzarote, Spain, 2006.
- [16] M. Zhao, S. He, H. Wang, G. Qin, An integrated fractional partial differential equation and molecular dynamics model of anomalously diffusive transport in heterogeneous nano-pore structures, *Journal of Computational Physics*, 373, pp.1000-1012, 2018.
- [17] F. Mainardi, *Fractional Calculus: Theory and Applications*, *Mathematics*, vol. 6, no. 9, 145, 2018.
- [18] C. -H. Yu, Using integration by parts for fractional calculus to solve some fractional integral problems, *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Research*, vol. 11, no. 2, pp. 1-5, 2023.
- [19] C. -H. Yu, Infinite series expressions for the values of some fractional analytic functions, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 80-85, 2023.
- [20] C. -H. Yu, Study of fractional analytic functions and local fractional calculus, *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 39-46, 2021.
- [21] C. -H, Yu, Evaluating fractional derivatives of two matrix fractional functions based on Jumarie type of Riemann-Liouville fractional derivative, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 39-43, 2024.
- [22] C. -H, Yu, Studying three types of matrix fractional integrals, *International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Innovations*, vol. 12, no. 4, pp. 35-39, 2024.
- [23] C. -H. Yu, Exact solutions of some fractional power series, *International Journal of Engineering Research and Reviews*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 36-40, 2023.